

Development of a Novel, Low-Cost Accelerometer System for Recording Vibration Propagation over the Skin

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Abstract. We present a novel accelerometer system, representing an advance in precisely measuring interactions humans have with objects. Our research aims to quantify skin vibration propagation by providing a cost-effective, scalable, and flexible solution. The system's innovative design allows for the modular inclusion of multiple accelerometers to suit specific research needs, making it highly adaptable for various experimental setups and recording from anatomical locations over the body. The core of our system is comprised of a networked array of low cost microcontrollers, each connected to up to 8 LIS3DH accelerometers via SPI communication. The system features a bespoke data synchronization solution that enhances robustness, while minimizing costs. The use of skin-friendly adhesive materials ensures the system's discreet integration into daily activities without hindering natural movement or comfort. Preliminary tests have successfully demonstrated the system's ability to capture detailed and accurate vibration waves across different skin areas, such as the hands and forearms. These findings underscore the potential of our system to progress haptic research by providing a detailed understanding of tactile feedback mechanisms without the limitations of traditional, more intrusive methods. Looking forward, we aim to incorporate wireless capabilities into our system to further extend its applicability across a wider spectrum of fields, including virtual reality, rehabilitative medicine, and tactile communication technologies. By enhancing the system's versatility and user-friendliness, our work sets a new standard in the study of haptic feedback, with far-reaching implications for both academic research and practical applications in enhancing human-computer interaction.

Keywords: Haptic Feedback, Skin Interactions, Wearable Technology.

1 Introduction

Recent advancements in haptic feedback technologies have highlighted the critical role of understanding vibration propagation on human skin, which is vital for enhancing our interactions with devices. Research has revealed the intricate nature of tactile feedback, showing aspects of touch reflected in vibration propagation beyond the initially

stimulated and contacted areas [1-4], which can be studied with a specialized tool that maps these vibrations during different interactions [5]. Despite these insights, the development of a robust, cost-effective, and unobtrusive system for recording such data remains challenging. Addressing this gap, our project introduces a novel, low-cost accelerometer system designed for minimal interference with user movement, aiming to capture detailed vibration data across multiple skin locations simultaneously. This approach meets the primary objective of economically and effectively recording vibration propagation and advances the practicality of haptic feedback research by accommodating the dynamic nature of human skin interaction.

2 Methods

The developed system employs an array of networked low-cost microcontrollers, each connected to up to eight LIS3DH accelerometers via SPI communication. The system features a custom data synchronization solution that enhances robustness, allows sampling alongside other signals, and reduces costs and the need for more complex system design. Figure 1 shows an example setup of the current system. Its discreet form factor, with adjustable connector lengths, allows for a personalized setup. This ensures the system's adaptability for various research needs and participant anatomies, optimizing data collection without compromising user comfort or movement. This digital system will be benchmarked against a standard analog system, also developed by the team. We plan to test a control population aged over 18 years old, with equal numbers of men and women, focusing on how vibrations from tactile interactions propagate over the hand and arm during different touch interactions. Design files for this accelerometer system will be made available as open source once its development is complete, with programs written in languages (C, Python) that are more well suited to end user development than previously used commercial solutions requiring commercial hardware and more in depth engineering experience (LABVIEW, Verilog).

Fig. 1. Example setup of the accelerometer system adapted to the hand and wrist, showing the multiple recording from six accelerometers.

3 Expected Results

We expect to demonstrate detailed and accurate vibrations induced from touch, without restricting the user's movements. The recordings should show precise synchronization between accelerometers and alongside other signals, which will be evaluated with paired recordings made with the analog version. We expect to obtain signals containing information specific to the touch interactions, with attenuation as a function of distance and physical properties of the interaction. Therefore, we predict to see specific vibration profiles as a function of the way in which a person interacts with an object, and the properties of the object itself.

4 Conclusion

Our accelerometer system marks an advancement in haptic technology, offering an affordable, scalable, and flexible solution for studying vibration propagation across the skin and body. It allows for the adjustment of the number of accelerometers and the form factor required at different body locations, facilitating in-depth research while being minimally intrusive and comfortable for the user. This innovation represents a significant step to enable development of more immersive and accessible haptic feedback technologies. For future versions, we aim to integrate wireless capabilities to further enhance its application across a broad spectrum, including virtual reality, rehabilitative medicine, and tactile communication technologies. This development promises to enrich our understanding of tactile interactions, as well as offering a versatile tool with far-reaching implications for both research and practical applications. For these reasons, we will be sharing this system as open access, so that the haptics community can benefit from it and advance scientific research.

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References

1. Manfredi, Louise R., et al. "The effect of surface wave propagation on neural responses to vibration in primate glabrous skin.", in *PloS one* 7.2, (2012)
2. Delhaye, Benoit, et al. "Texture-induced vibrations in the forearm during tactile exploration.", in *Frontiers in behavioral neuroscience*, (2012)
3. Shah VA, Casadio M, Scheidt RA, Mrotek LA. "Vibration Propagation on the Skin of the Arm", *Applied Sciences*, (2019)
4. K. Shao and L. Jones, "Mechanical and Psychophysical Studies of Surface Wave Propagation during Vibrotactile Stimulation", *IEEE Trans. Haptics*, (2013)
5. Y. Shao, H. Hu and Y. Visell, "A Wearable Tactile Sensor Array for Large Area Remote Vibration Sensing in the Hand," in *IEEE Sensors Journal*, (2020)